

UNIVERSITAT
RAMON LLULL

CoARA URL Action Plan 2025-2028

Approved by the Governing Board on June 12, 2025.

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1. Starting situation

Ramon Llull University (URL) is a private, non-profit university of a federal nature, which has been part of the International Coalition for the Advancement of Research Evaluation (CoARA) since its constitution in December 2022. This adhesion is part of the University's broader commitment to promote more equitable, qualitative and continuous improvement-oriented assessment, in line with the principles of responsible research and innovation of [the University's Strategic Framework](#).

At the same time, the URL is a signatory of the [Declaration on Research Assessment](#) (DORA), which claims the need to value research beyond bibliometric metrics, and also of the [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#), which emphasizes the social commitment of research and the promotion of open and inclusive research.

Among the commitments adopted with the accession to CoARA is the elaboration of a 4-year institutional Action Plan that responds to the [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#) signed. This Plan aims to avoid the misuse of quantitative measures that can favour malpractices and thus promote a culture of evaluation based on academic integrity, transparency and accountability.

This document includes the CoARA Action Plan of the Ramon Llull University for the period 2025-2028, approved by the Governing Board on June 12, 2025.

1.1. Background

The International Coalition for the Advancement of Research Assessment (CoARA) emerged in 2022 as a global initiative, based on the [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#) and signed at the time of writing this Plan by more than 800 organizations around the world. This international coalition, which brings together universities, research agencies and other entities, works to develop and promote a fairer, more transparent scientific evaluation model based on the actual quality of contributions, abandoning the reliance on quantitative indicators that often do not reflect the full richness of research.

In accordance with these principles, CoARA identifies ten key points ranging from the protection of scientific integrity and excellence to the recognition of disciplinary diversity, social impact and the need for collaboration and transparency in evaluation processes.

During the first year of activity, CoARA is organized into groups that address specific topics (e.g., academic career, infrastructure, multilingualism, responsible metrics, etc.), and also into national chapters. In the case of Spain, the [Spanish Chapter](#) was created, led by the National Agency for Quality Assessment and Accreditation (ANECA), the Conference of Rectors of Spanish Universities (CRUE) and the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), with the support of the Ministry of Universities, first, and the Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities. later.

At the state level, during 2023 the contributions and regulatory modifications regarding academic evaluation are noteworthy. On the one hand, the new Organic Law of the University System (LOSU) incorporates modifications in the accreditation of teaching staff and specific criteria regarding the promotion of Open Science that must be incorporated into the evaluation by quality agencies. On the other hand, the first [National](#)

[Open Science Strategy \(ENCA\) 2023-2027](#) contemplates, as one of the strategic objectives, the establishment of new research evaluation mechanisms and a system of incentives and recognitions that should promote Open Science practices. In order to incorporate these regulatory changes, ANECA constitutes the evaluation and monitoring commission of the state accreditation procedure and thus be able to comply with the commitments made with DORA and CoARA.

1.2. The evaluation of research and teaching staff at the Ramon Llull University

Currently, the evaluation of research and teaching staff at the URL is based on quantitative and qualitative criteria. However, the diversity of institutions and centers resulting from the federal nature of the University represents a challenge to harmonize these criteria. In addition, the URL is a generalist university that integrates a wide range of fields of knowledge, from the social sciences and humanities to engineering, health sciences and the arts, each with its own scientific traditions, knowledge production models and quality standards. This richness and diversity of disciplines also pose a challenge when it comes to harmonizing research evaluation processes, since it is necessary to ensure that the criteria applied in each field are relevant and recognize the particularities of each area. This Action Plan seeks to establish common principles, respecting the uniqueness of each of the centres and the disciplinary diversity of the University.

2. Action Plan 2025-2028

2.1. Premises for the construction of the Plan

The URL Action Plan for the achievement of CoARA commitments has been designed based on the following premises:

- **Commitment to CoARA:** All actions of the Plan always include the four commitments that represent the core of the reform proposal and that are translated as:
 1. Recognize the variety of research contributions.
 2. Prioritize qualitative evaluations, making responsible use of quantitative indicators where appropriate.
 3. Abandon the inappropriate use of metrics such as the *Journal Impact Factor* or the h-index.
 4. Avoid making use of ranking data in the evaluation of research.
- **Progressive application:** Progressively incorporate the regulatory changes introduced by the LOSU, with an overall view.
- **Internal participation:** Involve the different groups of the URL community affected by this Plan, in the entire process of design, execution and monitoring.
- **Benchmarking:** To participate in relevant national and international forums that allow us to compare ourselves with similar and related institutions, and to collect the derived good practices.
- **Evaluation and continuous improvement:** Carry out pilot actions and review the Plan periodically, making use of good national and international practices.

2.2. Proposed Action Plan

The priority actions of the URL Action Plan 2025-2028 are summarized in the following table:

COARA's COMMITMENTS	OBJECTIVES	ACTIONS	DESCRIPTION / KEY TASKS	RESPONSIBLE	CALENDAR	FOLLOW-UP EVIDENCE
5. Commit resources to the reform of research evaluation, which is necessary to achieve the organizational changes that have been assumed.	Coordinate the actions of the Plan.	0. Annual follow-up	To monitor the actions of the Plan and to report in a timely manner to the University's Governing Bodies.	Vice-Rector for Research and Innovation	2025-2028	Minutes of the meetings of the Governing Bodies of the URL.
6. Review and develop criteria, tools and processes for research evaluation.	To have a space to reflect on the categories of teaching staff and the evaluation criteria.	1. Creation of the Internal Faculty Working Group	Establish a schedule of regular meetings.	Vice-Rector for Research and Innovation, Rector's Delegate for Faculty Affairs	2025	No. of meetings held.
	Harmonize categories and access routes.		Analyse the existing categories and their access procedure.		2025-2026	New regulations on access to categories.
	Promote more inclusive and equitable criteria in the evaluation of teachers.		Propose incorporating indicators of social impact, interdisciplinarity and teaching quality.		2025-2026	Document with new proposal of categories.
			Make it easier to use Altmetric in the URL community to drive new metrics.		2025-2028	Metrics tracking report (Altmetric).
			Propose modifications to internal regulations, in accordance with CoARA.		2025-2026	New articles incorporated into the regulations.

COARA's COMMITMENTS	OBJECTIVES	ACTIONS	DESCRIPTION / KEY TASKS	RESPONSIBLE	CALENDAR	FOLLOW-UP EVIDENCE
	To promote the principles of Open Science in relation to research results.	2. Creation of the Open Science Working Group	Develop an Open Science URL policy.	Head of the Office of Research and Innovation	2025-2026	Approval of the regulations.
			Incorporate monitoring indicators into relevant reports.		2025-2028	Report on the evolution of Open Science principles to research results.
	Track the use of tools to promote Open URL Science.		Facilitate and promote the use of DAUs, the DMP tool, and the CORA data repository. RDR.		2025-2028	
	Reform the criteria for calls for the selection and evaluation of personnel and projects.	3. Update internal calls adapted to CoARA principles	Review and update the bases of calls to include qualitative and responsible criteria.	Vice-Rector for Research and Innovation	2025-2028	No. of reformulated calls.
7. Raise awareness of research evaluation reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on evaluation criteria and processes, and on the use to be made.	Ensure the dissemination and effective adoption of the new evaluation criteria and processes.	4. Communication and training strategy	Write clear guidelines on evaluation criteria and good practices.	Head of the Office of Research and Innovation	2025 2027	No. of training sessions carried out.
			Organize annual training sessions for PDI and PTGAS.			% of participation (PDI and PTGAS).
8. To exchange practices and experiences that allow mutual learning inside and outside CoARA.	Stay in touch with the coalition, its progress and new developments.	5. Participation in the CoARA General Assembly	Participation in the CoARA general assembly.	Vice-Rector for Research and Innovation	2025-2028	Annual summary of participation in CoARA.

COARA's COMMITMENTS	OBJECTIVES	ACTIONS	DESCRIPTION / KEY TASKS	RESPONSIBLE	CALENDAR	FOLLOW-UP EVIDENCE
	Contribute to the national discussion.	6. Participation in the Spanish chapter of CoARA	Attend meetings and workshops of the <i>Spanish Chapter</i> led by ANECA.	Vice-Rector for Research and Innovation	2025-2028	No. meetings/workshops attended.
9. Communicate progress and adherence to the principles and implementation of commitments.	Benefit from shared good practices.		Share experiences and documentation with other universities.			Concrete proposals applied to the URL.
10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the most current research on research evaluation, with open data to collect evidence and generate new research.			Adapt the recommendations received to the reality of the URL.			
	Run pilot evaluation tests that serve as a basis for testing and analysis.	7. Follow-up of success stories or evaluation proposals that are innovative	Follow-up of pilot tests within the URL.	Vice-Rector for Research and Innovation	2025-2028	No. of actions implemented.

2.3. Governance and monitoring

- **Responsibility:** The Vice-Rector for Research and Innovation will coordinate the Plan, with the support of the Working Group-Faculty and the Head of the Research and Innovation Office of the URL.
- **Monitoring:** Annual reports will be presented to the Governing Team and the University's governing bodies.
- **Evaluation:** A six-monthly review of the actions implemented will be carried out and the Plan will be adjusted according to the needs detected.